

A Study on Need of Structural and Procedural Changes in the Inclusive Education: A Possible Challenge

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ABSTRACT: *Currently, the inclusion process has challenged educational systems to make fundamental changes in their procedures and structures, as it has increasingly been necessary to build a school in an inclusive perspective that serves students with different characteristics, potentials and learning rhythms. This study aims to investigate the process of inclusion of students with disabilities in the school environment, understanding the proposal of the inclusive school, discussing the distinctions that involve the processes of inclusion and exclusion, as well as reflecting on the importance of the educator and the need for a adequate training that contributes to the development of an education that respects diversity To carry out the study, a qualitative approach and field research was carried out in a school of the municipal education network, the U.E.B. Gov. Jackson Kepler Lago, having as subjects involved the professionals of that school, with the intention of knowing their conceptions and practices regarding inclusion. The structured interview and direct observation in the classroom were used as data collection instruments. The work was based on the following theorists: Vygotsky; Oak; among others. The methodology enabled the identification of barriers to be overcome by these professionals for the realization of inclusive education. It is concluded that the inclusion of students with disabilities in the researched school still does not happen satisfactorily, there is a lack of adequate training for teachers, school structure, psycho-pedagogical monitoring and a curriculum directed to the needs of these students, among others. , hindering an adequate development to the real needs of the same ones.*

Keywords: Inclusion. Inclusive School. Pedagogical practices.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of school inclusion is very broad and complex. Historically, the discriminatory existence of the school and of all society is limited to the schooling of a select and homogeneous group of people. Those who did not belong to this group were excluded from this society. With the democratization of the school, the inclusion/exclusion contradiction arises.

In the general sense, inclusion is not restricted to the inclusion of students with motor, sensory or cognitive disabilities, but extends to all individuals in the educational process. Then, access for people with disabilities to schools begins, but in a process of integration and not of inclusion. All this modification, although slow and not very significant, promotes future and important changes in the scenario for attempts at inclusive education (BRASIL, 2008).

Challenges are faced when it comes to social inclusion, and this demands an intense work to raise awareness of the need to integrate people with disabilities into regular schools.

Faced with all the difficulties in implementing the Inclusive School in Brazil, there is the coexistence between disabled and non-disabled students who have the possibility of learning to live with the differences present in the community.

The objective of this work is to understand the challenges that are present in the process of building an inclusive school.

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The study was also carried out, through bibliographic research, with several theorists discussing the theme of inclusive education.

II. HISTORICAL CONTEXTUALIZATION OF INCLUSION IN BRAZIL

The theme of inclusion has been widely debated, due to its complexity. It needs to be approached with complete objectivity, without prejudice, and with interest and affection implicit in the act of educating, but without sentimentalism. The topic is the subject of many debates, the result of a historical evolution, which comes from discussions of many, many years.

The idea of an inclusive society is based on a philosophy that recognizes and values diversity, as an inherent characteristic of the constitution of any society. Based on this principle and having as a horizon the ethical scenario of Human Rights, it signals the need to guarantee the access and participation of all, to all opportunities, regardless of the peculiarities of each individual and/or social group.

Personal identity is built on the fabric of social relationships that permeate their everyday existence. Thus, efforts must be made to ensure that relationships between individuals are characterized by attitudes of mutual respect, represented by the appreciation of each person in their uniqueness, that is, in the characteristics that constitute them.

The awareness of the right to constitute one's own identity and the recognition of the other's identity translates into the right to equality and respect for differences, ensuring differentiated opportunities (equity), as many as necessary, with a view to the pursuit of equality (MEC/SEESP, 2001).²

Therefore, for equality to be real, it must be relative. This means that people are different, have different needs and compliance with the law requires that they be guaranteed the appropriate conditions to meet individual peculiarities, so that everyone can enjoy the existing opportunities. In this regard, the Federal Constitution of 1988 assumes:

The principle of equality as a fundamental pillar of a democratic and fair society, when it says in the caput of its Article 5 that "all are equal before the law, without distinction of any nature, guaranteeing Brazilians and foreigners residing in the country, the inviolability of the right to life, liberty, equality, security and property" (BRASIL, 1988).³

Even though legislation has advanced a lot in terms of aspects related to inclusion, it is crucial to understand the historical aspects and the main legal frameworks that point to the trajectory of inclusive education and that allowed the achievements to be possible.

2.1 Historical aspects and legal frameworks of inclusion

Over many years, efforts have been made to ensure that educational care for students with disabilities has a positive response and this transformation took place due to fierce social struggles.

The General Assembly of the United Nations - UN produced several guiding documents for the development of public policies of its member countries. Brazil, as a member country of the UN and signatory of

² Translated by author.

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these documents, recognizes their contents and has respected them, in the elaboration of internal public policies. The United Nations General Assembly, in 1948, proclaimed the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, in which it recognizes that:

All human beings are born free and equal, in dignity and rights... (Article 1º, ... without any distinction, namely race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, wealth, birth or any other situation" (Art.2). In its Article 7. It proclaims that "all are equal before the law, and without distinction are entitled to equal protection of the law...". In Article 26, it proclaims, in item I, that "everyone has the right to education. Education must be free, at least that corresponding to basic elementary education. Elementary education is mandatory. Technical and professional education must be generalized...", in item 2, establishes that "education must aim at the full expansion of the human personality and the reinforcement of human rights and fundamental freedoms and must promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations and all racial or religious groups..." Article 27 proclaims, in item 1, that "everyone has the right freely to take part in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to participate on scientific progress and the benefits that flow from it (UNIVERSAL DECLARATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS, 1948).⁴

In general, this Declaration guarantees to persons with disabilities the same rights to liberty, to a dignified life, to basic education, to personal and social development and to free participation in community life.

There was a movement in the rights of minorities that characterized the 60's, all of this linked to large protests due to prejudices associated with the paradigm of Institutionalization of people with mental illness and people with disabilities, thus giving a new path to this new relationship from which social groups originated that were willing to face this opportunity to give a voice and a voice to those people who were on the margins of society and who were not assisted by any public policy.

Inclusive Education began to be discussed from the Salamanca Declaration elaborated in 1994, which addressed a process of school inclusion and an egalitarian education for all who were excluded due to disability, social or financial. Its objective was to ensure that the special educational needs of individuals were respected, and the situation of accessibility began to be discussed and implemented in schools around the world. between people, whether they have some kind of disability or not.

Schools must welcome all children, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other conditions. They must accommodate children with disabilities and gifted children; children living on the streets and working; children from distant or nomadic populations; children from linguistic, ethnic or cultural minorities and children 7 from other disadvantaged or marginalized groups or areas (Declaration of Salamanca, 1994, p. 17-18).⁵

In this context, this declaration begins to guide paths and attitudes to develop quality education for all individuals in all educational institutions.

Inclusive education stems from the movement of struggle that until today has to be seen by everyone from the doorman to the teacher in the classroom this struggle will always exist, because it is clear that there is inclusion in the school, but will the student participate in this inclusion in the classroom itself?

⁴ Translated by autor

⁵ Translated by author

There is no ready recipe for that teacher who received students with disabilities in the school year, the recipe is to prepare for this student, take courses, training courses offered, the government needs to help many institutions that lack specialized teaching material, for this child with a disability and show that they can all learn equally and within their limitations.

Each child has their characteristics, their interests, their abilities and needs to learn that are of their own personality in their common way, what we call natural. Institutions have to adapt to the needs of this child and we know that these programs are applied and directed to this child, who wants to follow an adequate rhythm in which they can reach everyone without distinction. that must integrate them into a centralized pedagogy capable of meeting these needs.

Schools with this integrative didactics represent the most effective way to combat discriminatory attitudes, to create a receptive classroom where everyone can understand that they are equal, but different physically and mentally, to build an integrative society and provide education for all, fulfilling with which the student himself grows respecting his neighbor.

Soon after the Salamanca Declaration, in Brazil, the Law of Directives and Bases of National Education - LDBN nº 9394/96 was approved. That law determines that people with special educational needs are included in regular education schools (BRAZIL, 1996). It is stressed that the Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988, in article 208, already referred to the care of students with special needs, “preferably” in Regular Education classes.

The LDB, in chapter V, defines special education as a type of school education, preferably offered in the regular school system, for people with special needs (art. 58). The provision of special education is a “constitutional duty of the State” (art. 58, § 3).

The National Curriculum Parameters (PCNs) in 1998 – Curricular Adaptations: assistance to people with special educational needs highlighted the right to education in view of the diversity of subjects that make up the Brazilian school.

A person's right to education is protected by national education policy regardless of gender, ethnicity, age or social class. Access to school goes beyond the act of enrollment and implies appropriation of knowledge and educational opportunities offered to all students with a view to achieving the purposes of education, despite the diversity in the school population (BRAZIL, 1998, p. 15).⁶

It is emphasized that the concept of inclusion defended by the PCNs, when observing that access to school “implies appropriation of knowledge and educational opportunities offered to all students”. In this sense, it cannot be said that access to school is synonymous with inclusion, but it is understood that inclusion depends on the appropriation of school knowledge as an opportunity to overcome inequality.

Decree No. 3,298, which regulates Law No. 7,853/89, signed in 1999, provides for the National Policy for the Integration of Persons with Disabilities, where Special Education is defined as “a transversal modality at all levels and modalities of education”. teaching, emphasizing the complementary role of special education to regular education” (BRAZIL, 2006, p. 3).

The National Policy on Special Education from the perspective of inclusive education (2008) provides for the rights of people with special educational needs and advocates the principles of education for all, and at least in terms of “access and permanence” they begin to consolidate school inclusion. of that student.

According to this policy, students with special educational needs must be included in common teaching classes, thus, for the current national policy of special education in the perspective of inclusive education:

Special education is a teaching modality that permeates all levels, stages and modalities, provides specialized educational services, provides services and

⁶ Translated by author

resources specific to this service and guides students and their teachers regarding their use in regular classes (PNNEPI, 2008, p.16).⁷

Therefore, it is necessary that education systems ensure special curricula and techniques, as well as teaching methods and resources that help the teaching-learning process of these special students, at different levels of regular education.

In 2009, the National Education Council – CNE published Resolution CNE/CEB, 04/2009, which establishes the Operational Guidelines for Specialized Educational Assistance – AEE, highlighting that this is a Special Education service that organizes pedagogical resources and accessibility so that students with special needs have an effective participation articulated with the regular school, although their activities are different from those carried out in common teaching classrooms (BRAZIL, 2011).

In general, the legislation is concerned with ensuring that the education necessary for the development of their potentiality is provided to the student and as an element of self-fulfillment, in the qualification for work and preparation for the conscious exercise of citizenship.

It is noted that, in Brazil, laws define and organize conceptions and forms of service, but when one observes the practice, one sees that it is still very far from what is foreseen in the legislation and ensuring these rights becomes increasingly a reason for claims by social movements and the entire population, since it is the duty of power public to promote quality education for all.

It is essential that the school works to the maximum the competences of these students, in all areas of knowledge so that they develop the necessary skills for their experience in the world and, only with the commitment of the public power these educational practices will be possible.

In Brazil, about 10% of the population has some type of disability, making it essential that the Brazilian educational system is organized and structured so that these people have access to and stay in school assured.

The 2018 School Census, carried out by the Anízio Teixeira Institute (INEP) reveals advances in special education services. The enrollment of students with disabilities, pervasive developmental disorders and/or high abilities/giftedness in ordinary (included) or special exclusive classes reached 1.2 million in 2018, an increase of 33.2% compared to 2014. Considering only students from 4 to 17 years of age in special education, it appears that the percentage of enrollments of students included in regular classes has also been increasing gradually, from 87.1% in 2014 to 92.1% in 2018 (INEP, 2018).

Although practices reveal that the country is still far from complying with the legislation, the data reveal that special education services have grown in regular schools, although it cannot be said that inclusion is effectively happening in these schools.

The inclusion process, however, is not easily achieved only through the establishment of laws. Nor can it be concluded quickly, it requires a series of gradual measures to reformulate education with regard to the right to education so that no child suffers restrictions in their access to school.

According to Fetback and Baldin (2014), the different historical contexts, the transformations in the different spheres of social life, and the new behaviors have enabled a new perception about people with disabilities.

The effectiveness of guaranteeing the rights of people with disabilities, at school has encountered barriers due to the historical conceptions of exclusion, that are still present today. To change this reality is a challenge portrayed to education systems and society as a whole. And, in an attempt to eliminate prejudices, create opportunities for insertion, integrate students with differences in common schools, social movements gained representation and converted their desires and needs into rights.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion

⁷ Translated by author

The path from exclusion to inclusion of children and young people with disabilities is linked to the economic, social and cultural characteristics of each stage experienced, which are decisive for the way in which difference is understood.

Exclusion, segregation, integration and, nowadays, inclusion, mark a path, to which are underlying concepts and practices, in relation to which, in the case of inclusion, understood as inclusive education, teacher training is one of the fundamental factors for its Implementation.

According to Silva (2009), in the Middle Ages, many people with disabilities were victims of persecution, judgment and executions, since they attributed the image of these people to the intervention of demonic forces, to acts of witchcraft and sorcery, since the society of time was dominated by religion, they believed that man should be the "image and likeness of God", that is, perfect.

Many years later, considering the Brazilian context, with the democratization of education that allowed education to be more accessible to a large part of the population, since access to school became a right for all. However, people who had disabilities that limited their performance in the job market, or who were different from what was imposed by society, were excluded, being isolated from any social activity.

Until recently, the existence of special schools was very common, as Beyer (2006) reports that in addition to special schools being seen as segregating spaces, they still play the role of 'deposit' for rejected, failed and disabled people, whose performance does not satisfy the rule of the regular curriculum" (p.21)

Gradually, these spaces ceased to exist, although it is still possible to find them, as the path to inclusion went through a set of decisions and measures taken within international organizations and agencies, such as the United Nations and UNESCO, which were of fundamental importance in the progressive introduction of social policies favorable to their implementation.

In Brazil, people with disabilities began to receive educational assistance from the creation of the *Instituto dos Meninos Cegos*, in 1845, and the *Instituto dos Surdos Mudos*, in 1857. Later, the *Pestalozzi Institute* was created, where people with mental disabilities were attended, The Association of Parents and Friends of the Exceptional was also founded in 1945.

For Ferreira (2006) "inserting the disabled student into a school that has not been resized within a new paradigm means continuing the process of exclusion...". In this sense, it is not enough just to ensure the physical presence of children with disabilities in regular schools, they need to be an effective part of the teaching-learning process, for that, the school needs to reflect on how to include them. This generates changes in pedagogical practices rooted in traditional forms of teaching.

It is also noted the need to adapt teaching methods, pedagogical means, curricula, human and material resources, as well as educational spaces, to carry out a truly inclusive intervention with students, respecting their individuality, involving the participation of families as essential step for student development.

In this way, the acceptance and appreciation of diversity, cooperation and learning in the midst of differences constitute values that guide inclusion, understood as the process by which society adapts in order to be able to include, in all its spaces, people with disabilities and, at the same time, they need school to prepare themselves in order to play their role in society and exercise their citizenship.

The inclusion assumes that all students are at school to learn and, therefore, participate and interact with each other, regardless of the limitations they have, and it is up to the school to adapt, being a great challenge to create situations that favor the student learning.

For the effectiveness of inclusion, it is necessary that some changes occur both in the posture and pedagogical practices of the teacher, as well as in the infrastructure of the space where the child is inserted, because people with disabilities need adequate spaces, specific pedagogical resources. and qualified teachers, which are guaranteed by the National Policy on Special Education from the Perspective of Inclusive Education (2008).

According to Beyer (2006) school inclusion requires a new way of thinking, because we know that children are different from each other, each with their own way of thinking and learning, given that everyone is special.

The same author also says that the inclusive education project must be constituted as a project with well-defined characteristics or principles, but that allows revisions, redefinitions, and resignifications throughout the school implementation process (BEYER, 2006). This school needs to be a means of enabling students with special educational needs to reach levels of development that justify their inclusion in the school.

Mantoan (2005) states that inclusion is our ability to understand and recognize the other and, thus, have the privilege of living and sharing with people who are different from us. Inclusive education welcomes all people without exception. It is for the physically disabled student, for the mentally impaired, for the gifted, for all minorities and for the child who is discriminated against for any other reason. I often say that being together is crowding at the movies, on the bus and even in the classroom with people we don't know. Inclusion is being with, interacting with the other. (MANTOAN, 2005, p.24)

Cunha (2015, p. 69), "to include is much more than to insert. In addition, it is necessary to provide conditions for permanence and the possibility of learning development, thus maximizing its potential"

From the contribution of Mantoan and Cunha, it is evident that inclusion is still a challenge for school institutions, considering that it is not only a matter of legal obligation in enrollment, nor in the accessible physical structure, this process undergoes profound changes in the understanding of what actually is to include, so that these people have the right to fully develop.

III. SCHOOL AND THE INCLUSION PROCESS

Throughout history, processes of exclusion have been disseminated, as seen in the previous chapter, as a result of conceptions and practices that have reinforced marginalization and prejudice in relation to the "different", among which are people with disabilities.

The inclusion movement is the result of a series of public policies aimed at diversity. Those documents were written based on the principles of equal rights and education for all, proposals that gained strength in international congresses such as the World Conference on Education for all, which took place in Jomtien in 1990 and, later, the World Conference on Special Education held in Salamanca in 1994, of which Brazil was a signatory.

The principles of inclusion, based on the Salamanca Declaration, advocate school practices without any type of discrimination against the person, whether by race, language, ethnicity, gender, culture, religion and disability, among others, and idealizes a school capable of attending the students' specific needs, through pedagogical practices focused on diversity, respecting and valuing difference.

By the force of law, the school is required to accept students with disabilities, whether they are prepared to receive them, and create an environment that favors their development so that they accompany classes, integrate with other students, only then, the school can begin to build an inclusive work.

It is the school's role to favor the learning of students with disabilities. This role also includes providing didactic material, equipment, appropriate rooms and staff prepared or at least attentive to any possible need for student assistance.

According to the UNESCO report, prepared by the International Commission on Education for the 21st Century, the pillars of education are defined as: learning to know; learn to do; learn to live together and learn to be.

To establish inclusive education in all these pillars is to realize that students with disabilities will learn through different means and that they can find in that school a teaching aimed at everyone, from which, they themselves do not feel excluded with activities different from other students.

Learning to know is about the search for knowledge, which makes us want to learn. *Learning to do* is related to practice, the acquisition of skills to do something. *Learning to live together* prioritizes respect for others, pluralism of ideas, cooperation. *Learning to be* is about understanding yourself, introspection. And, knowing these pillars is essential to implement a quality inclusive practice focused on student development.

Students with disabilities are assisted by special education, which is a teaching modality in accordance with current legislation, which aims to promote the development of people with disabilities, who need

specialized care, respecting individual differences, in order to guarantee them the full exercise of basic citizen rights and effective social integration.

Providing students with disabilities with the promotion of their abilities involving the full development of their personality, active participation in social life and in the world of work, are the main objectives of special education and as well as bio-psychic development, providing learning that leads to this educating to greater autonomy.

Another fact of extreme importance for special education is the fact that the teacher must consider the student as a person full of potential to learn and socialize, who have wills and affections, and these must be respected.

For Mantoan (2006, p. 19), “inclusive education can be defined as the practice of including everyone regardless of talent, disability, socioeconomic or cultural background, in schools and classrooms where the needs of these students are met”.

Therefore, inclusion is a movement that seeks to rethink the school so that it goes from being a school of discrimination to being open to all. However, it is recognized that it is not enough to simply physically insert students into the school, it is necessary to have adequate classrooms, libraries, bathrooms and inclusive access, it also needs a formalized Pedagogical Political Project and, mainly, prepared teachers, and students willing to live with this new reality.

Special education is for by law, and today its precepts are based on inclusive education, and on the right acquired after various movements of struggle and social pressure for the realization of the conquest by the human rights movements and their representations. The guarantee of access to education and permanence in the school require the practice of a policy of respect for individual differences.

According to the Federal Constitution, in Title III, THE RIGHT TO EDUCATION AND THE DUTY TO EDUCATE, in art. 4th item III (1998, p.41), students with special needs are those who have unusual needs and, therefore, are different from other students in terms of curricular learning compatible with their ages and precisely, for this reason, these students need own pedagogical and methodological resources.

The school must propose to elaborate a course plan that will support the teacher in the elaboration of their planning, which can only be done based on the knowledge of the concrete reality of their students and the means they have at their disposal. Teacher training should also be prioritized, in order to support the teacher in proposing activities that lead to the achievement of various goals in the affective, cognitive and psychomotor domains, with the school being responsible for exploring, in working with students, the maximum possibilities of all the learning experiences.

To understand the true meaning of the inclusive school, which neither segregates nor excludes, we have to admit that:

Inclusion is NOT just about placing a disabled child in a classroom or school. This is just the smallest piece of the puzzle. Inclusion is about how we deal with diversity, how we deal with difference, how we deal with (or avoid dealing with) our morality. [...] Inclusion absolutely does NOT mean that we are all the same. Inclusion does celebrate our diversity and differences with respect and gratitude. The greater our diversity is, the richer our ability to create new ways of seeing the world (Forest, 1997).⁸

In view of the above, the challenge of understanding and implementing inclusive practices at school is evident, eliminating the processes of exclusion that prevents many people from having access to the right to education, and, among these challenges, one can highlight the training of teachers.

⁸ Translated by author

3.1 The role of teachers in the inclusion process

Among the concerns that schools express, the difficulty of teachers in conducting a teaching and learning process with students with disabilities is also a relevant aspect. Thus, it is necessary to invest in training to equip these teachers.

It is noted that undergraduate courses do not prepare future teachers to deal with the differences and particularities of each student.

It is important to emphasize that the training of teachers for their performance is based on the Law of Directives and Bases of Education n° 9.394/1996, which has as one of its legal foundations:

Art. 61. Sole paragraph. The training of education professionals, in order to meet the specificities of the exercise of their activities, as well as the objectives of the different stages and modalities of basic education, will be based on: (Included by Law No. 12.014, of 2009)

I – the presence of solid basic training, which provides knowledge of the scientific and social foundations of their work skills; (Included by Law No. 12,014 of 2009)

II – the association between theories and practices, through supervised internships and in-service training; (Included by Law No. 12,014 of 2009)

III – the use of previous training and experiences, in educational institutions and in other activities. (Included by Law No. 12,014 of 2009) (BRAZIL, 1996).⁹

Regarding continuing education, this must permeate its practice with students, based on transdisciplinary work with a permanent support team. It is essential to consider and value the knowledge of all education professionals in the inclusion process. It is not just about including a student, but about rethinking the contours of the school and what kind of education these professionals have been dedicated to. It is about triggering a collective process that seeks to understand the reasons why many children and adolescents also cannot find a “place” at school (BRAZIL, 2005, p.21).

Although legally supported, teachers have not received, either in graduation, or in effective exercise, training that allows their instrumentalization to work with people with disabilities, as well as the opportunity to review their practices so that they “reinvent” themselves: their actions, their procedures, its methodologies, its didactics and mainly aspects of valorization of its personal and professional development for the exercise of this profession.

Freire (2005) in his work *Pedagogy of Autonomy* states that

The ideal is that in the educational experience, students, educators and educators, together ‘live’ in such a way with the knowledge that they become wisdom. Something that is not strange to educators (FREIRE, 2005, p. 58).¹⁰

To build a school that adequately serves students with disabilities, considering their own characteristics, it is not enough just to have teachers and other professionals that a normal school has. It is necessary that this group of collaborators be able to perform this function, meeting the real need of each student.

In this context, Freire (2005) evidence that the teacher is the mediator and together (teacher and student) they approach knowledge, insofar as the teacher promotes pedagogical situations favorable to learning and in this exchange, both learn. This initiative encourages students with disabilities to overcome common sense and advance in their affective human potential.

⁹ Translated by author

¹⁰ Translated by author

The articulation between educators is urgent, as there is a need for a redefinition of the teacher's role and of their way of acting, in systemic thinking. It is necessary to think of learning as a cooperative and transformational process that provides the formation of students inserted in the world, and no longer in just a local community. Finally, think about education in relation to aspects of ethics, aesthetics and politics; education based on a democratic ideal (FARFUS, 2008, p. 30).

Agreeing with the author, it is believed in the importance of teachers joining forces so that pedagogical practices have a transformation, are updated, through a vision that no one learns anything alone and that together, teachers can develop an action in groups, from knowledge focused on inclusive education.

Inclusive education today is a challenge for teachers, as it forces them to rethink their way of teaching, their culture, their politics and their pedagogical strategies, adopting a receptive attitude towards the singularity that they will find in the classroom, having to detect potentialities and expose skills according to the demand that each student presents.

And it is only through the expansion of his view made possible by training that the teacher will be able to understand that theory and practice are "two sides of the same coin", that theory helps him to better understand his practice and to give it meaning and, consequently, that practice provides a better understanding of the theory or, even, reveals the need to be based on it.

IV. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

During this research, it was found that inclusion is of paramount importance for the better development of children, as it was observed that the teacher has an extremely judicious role in noting that the student with a disability needs to integrate and be inserted not only in school, but inside the classroom and that, in a way, the work of these teachers has to take place in a more integrated way.

Still, the need for qualification through training was detected so that teachers are properly qualified to deal with the student, increasing their interest, participation and motivation.

The research result also considered that there is a lot of difficulty in presenting activities aimed at inclusion and the teacher needs to develop or build new proposals that consider the specificities of their students, so that everyone can achieve success.

Using teaching and learning methods that go beyond lessons and textbooks can help get students to learn better from a combination of resources properly orchestrated by the teacher.

In this way, the different theoretical contributions of the different authors studied and cited during the study indicate that to improve learning, more attention should be paid to how we can build an inclusive school not only with regard to the physical structure, but to an entire pedagogical project. oriented towards inclusion.

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